

Demystification of Big Bang cosmology Myth

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Abstract

A given theory is alive when supported by experimental data. When a theory is based only on the interpretation of experimental data, it might be born dead without the scientific community being aware of it. This is the case of Big Bang cosmology, which has no support in a single astronomical observation. The aim of this article is the demystification of the Big Bang cosmology myth.

Keywords: CMB, cosmological redshift, expansion of the space

1. Introduction

CMB is the radiation of the universal space. The entire universal space radiates CMB that is highly uniform throughout the entire space. CMB has a thermal black body spectrum at a temperature of 2.72548 ± 0.00057 K. This is the result of the measurement that allows us to conclude that universal space radiates CMB. The interpretation of CMB as the relict radiation of the recombination period is only a hypothesis, it is not a scientific fact. In Big Bang cosmology, CMB is understood as proof of the model itself, which is a methodological error. Cosmological redshift is another astronomical observation that Big Bang cosmology has turned in its favor. Measurement of the cosmological redshift does not prove that the universe is expanding, it only proves that light coming from distant galaxies has a loss of energy [1].

Imagine a house made out of reddish bricks. Bricks are building the house, not the color. CMB and cosmological redshift are only the color, and we see them as bricks of the universe. On the basis of CMB and cosmological redshift, no realistic cosmological model can be built. The third proof of the Big Bang model is a myth has a mathematical character. FLWR metric is not valid for Euclidean space and NASA has measured universal space has a Euclidean shape. The Metric of Euclidean space is such that it cannot expand and cannot shrink [2].

2. Demystification of Big Bang cosmology myth

Big Bang cosmology is a school case of how science should not work. The idea of some beginning with a big explosion is a myth, and all astronomical data are interpreted in a way that fits well with the myth.

The first step of demystification is to bring awareness of your inner image of Big Bang cosmology. The first picture you see in your inner vision when someone mentions cosmology is below:

Figure 1: Your inner vision of cosmology

Only a five-year-old child can have such magic, irrational imagination to think that the universe has exploded from nothing. And this is the time when your indoctrination has started. When you hear the word “CMB” you imagine a recombination period, when you hear the word “cosmological redshift” you imagine the galaxies are moving away from each other, and the universe is expanding. If you are an adult person free of imposed ideas from your childhood, you see that Big Bang cosmology is a childish idea.

Why do you never ask yourself a question about the fact that the redshift of light was never observed in an expanding space? We only observe light in a space that is stationary, we do not have a theoretical model that would be describing how light moves in an expanding space and has an energy loss. You never ask because you do not want trouble. Big Bang cosmology is the main frame in which your life runs and you are not willing to doubt it. Since your early childhood, the Big Bang model is with you, especially if your parents are scientists. People very rarely doubt what they perceive and experience in their first six years of life. Big Bang is encoded in your mind with the same strength as your nationality and faith.

Eminent physicists wrote articles about weak points of Big Bang cosmology [3,4,5,6], and still today in 2022 we teach this model at universities. Stationary cosmology explains well all astronomical data and has no unbridgeable problems with the beginning and still, it is not yet back in power. Stand up and get free of Big Bang nonsense.

3. Conclusions

Your scientific mind is a prism through which you experience the universe, society, and yourself. Clean this prism of all learned ideas and start thinking with your own mind. Be aware of the three pillars of physics: 1) perception, 2) creation of the model (mathematization of the phenomena you study), and 3) experiment that will prove or disprove your model. This is physics, all the rest is a myth, at best “mathematical philosophy”.

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